

Scientific and Technical Articles per Billion GDP in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "Global Innovation Index: Scientific and technical articles per billion PPP\$ GDP" represents the quantity of scientific and technical articles published for each billion dollars of GDP at purchasing power parity (PPP). This indicator is a measure of a country's research activity and scientific output relative to its economic capacity, using PPP to allow fair comparisons among countries with different economies and living costs. The indicator highlights a country's contribution to global research and innovation, as a higher number of scientific articles per GDP unit indicates a stronger emphasis on academic and technological research in relation to available economic resources. It is used to assess a country's capacity to generate scientific and technical knowledge and understand the efficiency with which economic resources are employed in research. High levels of this variable are often associated with advanced economies or countries with robust research infrastructures, while lower values may signal limitations in capacity or focus on scientific development relative to the available economic potential. The data covers the period between 2013 and 2022.

Scientific and Technical Articles per Billion GDP in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The 2022 Global Innovation Index data on scientific and technical articles per billion PPP\$ GDP shows notable variations among countries, indicating different levels of investment, research focus, and infrastructure supporting scientific output. At the top of the list, Iceland stands out with a score of 100, suggesting an exceptionally high volume of scientific and technical publications relative to GDP.

This position likely reflects Iceland's strategic focus on scientific research and a strong research environment, despite the relatively small size of its economy and population. Other countries such as Denmark, Slovenia, and Cyprus follow closely, each scoring above 80, indicating robust research and publication rates that contribute to the global scientific discourse. Northern European countries, including Denmark, Sweden, and Finland, also score highly, with scores ranging from 70 to 90. These countries are known for well-funded educational systems, significant government support for research, and high GDP per capita, likely contributing to their strong performance in generating scientific output. Switzerland, renowned for its innovation ecosystem, also holds a high position, underscoring its role as a hub for scientific and technical advancements, supported by public and private investment in research and development. Tunisia's position among the top 15, with a score of 68.3, is noteworthy and relatively high for a developing country. This result reflects Tunisia's strong commitment to scientific education and research investment, an effort that could serve as a model for other nations aiming to enhance scientific output despite limited resources. Similarly, Iran and Jordan, with scores of 62.9 and 50.1, respectively, suggest that even with constraints in some areas, these countries are prioritizing scientific research, recognizing the critical role of scientific advances for socio-economic development. In contrast, several advanced economies, including the United States, Japan, and Germany, rank much lower than expected, with scores below 40. The United States, for instance, scores 26.9, indicating that while it produces a significant volume of scientific articles overall, its output relative to its vast GDP appears lower than in smaller, high-scoring nations. This phenomenon may highlight a scaling effect, where larger economies, even with substantial scientific output, seem less productive in relative terms when the volume is compared to a high GDP.

Scientific and Technical Articles per Billion GDP in the Global Innovation Index from 2013 to 2022.

The analysis of data on scientific and technical articles per billion PPP\$ GDP in the Global Innovation Index from 2013 to 2022 reveals contrasting trends in research output relative to economic scale across countries. This indicator reflects both the capacity and emphasis that different economies place on research and development, and it highlights shifts that may be influenced by national priorities, economic resources, or structural challenges. Among the top performers in terms of growth, Yemen saw an increase from 3.9 to 23.8 articles, representing a notable growth of 510.26%. This growth, though from a low starting point, may indicate a recent prioritization of scientific research despite the country's challenging socio-economic and political conditions. Other countries with significant increases include Brunei, Qatar, Ecuador, and Peru, each achieving growth of over 300% in scientific output relative to GDP. This increase could be due to intensified national investments in education and research infrastructure, as well as international partnerships or collaborations that bolster local scientific capacity. Rwanda and Ethiopia also show significant progress, with increases of 166.02% and 154.84%, respectively. For these African nations, improvements in educational policies, international research collaborations, and investments in science and technology may contribute to their strong upward trends. These increases reflect a broader movement across parts of Africa to enhance the continent's scientific profile, promoting knowledge-based economies despite limited resources. In the Middle East and North Africa region, several countries also show notable improvements. Saudi Arabia, for example, increased from 13.6 to 29.5 articles per billion PPP\$ GDP, reflecting its Vision 2030 initiative, which emphasizes innovation and scientific research as part of a strategic move toward diversifying the economy beyond oil. Similarly, countries like Oman, Kuwait, and the United Arab Emirates show growth, likely due to a combination of government support, diversification strategies, and increased education funding, particularly in science and technology fields. On the opposite end, a number of countries exhibit significant declines in scientific output relative to GDP. Armenia experienced the largest decrease, with a drop of 55.5%, from 60.9 to 27.1 articles, indicating potential economic or structural challenges within its research sector. Countries such as Moldova, Zimbabwe, and Ukraine also saw substantial declines, which may be attributed to economic instability, reduced funding, or brain drain, where skilled researchers migrate abroad for better opportunities, thus depleting local research capacities.

Conclusions. The value of scientific and technical articles per billion GDP grew by 6.6% on average between 2013 and 2022 across the analyzed countries. The top performers were Yemen with +510.26%, Brunei Darussalam with +364.29%, Qatar with +362.50%, Ecuador with +362.50%, and Peru with +171.43%. The worst performers were Zimbabwe with -47.12%, Mali with -47.55%, Côte d'Ivoire with -51.16%, Armenia with -55.50%, and Moldova with -62.26%.

	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Yemen, Rep.	3,9	23,8	19,9	510,26
	Brunei Darussalam	4,2	19,5	15,3	364,29
	Qatar	4	18,5	14,5	362,50
	Ecuador	3,7	17,1	13,4	362,16
	Peru	2,8	7,6	4,8	171,43
Worse Performers	Zimbabwe	55,6	29,4	-26,2	-47,12
	Mali	14,3	7,5	-6,8	-47,55
	Cote d'Ivoire	8,6	4,2	-4,4	-51,16
	Armenia	60,9	27,1	-33,8	-55,50
	Moldova	25,7	9,7	-16	-62,26

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